

Quality Assessment of Vanaspati-Ghee and Blended-Oil Marketed in Balochistan, Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

Edible oil and vanaspati-ghee are essential components of the human diet; however, their quality and safety largely depend on proper processing, storage and regulatory compliance to national food safety standards. Current study aims to assess the physicochemical characteristics of commercial vanaspati-ghee (n=35) and blended-oil (n=58) from 17 different brands in each category, collected from across the province during monitory surveillance by Balochistan Food Authority, from Jan 2024 to Jan 2025.

The physicochemical parameters analyzed included, acid value, peroxide values, moisture content, p-anisidine value, iodine value, vitamin A content and refractive index.

Vanaspati-ghee had acid values ranging from 0.03 to 0.54 mg KOH/g. Peroxide 0.45-13.17 meq O₂/kg, p-anisidine 0.5-7.8, moisture content 0.11-3.3%, Totox value 1.4 to 65, refractive index 1.44-1.46, iodine 2.0-60 gI₂/100g. Reference to vit A, approximately 23% of the samples were found in regulatory compliance to national food standard specifications. Similarly blended-oil had, acid values ranging between 0.03-11.10 mg KOH/g, peroxide 0.1-18.2 meq O₂/kg, p-anisidine 1.0-11, Totox 1.1 to 40.7, moisture 0.08-2.16%, refractive index 1.44-1.46, iodine values 2.00-80.00 gI₂/100g, while only 14% vit A compliance.

The study is the first study of its kind with Balochistan's perspective, highlighting substantial quality deterioration and regulatory non-compliance to standards across the product categories. Approximately 80% of the vanaspati-ghee and 100% blended-oil samples collected were found non-compliant to national food safety standard specifications. Quality deterioration largely attributed to oxidative degradation, excessive moisture and poor fortification practices, emphasizing the need for stringent post-production handling, improved storage and regular monitoring to ensure product stability and nutritional quality for consumer safety.

INTRODUCTION

Cooking oil and vanaspati-ghee are essential dietary component worldwide, not only because of their sensory characteristics, but also as source of energy for the body, medium for the transport of fat soluble vitamins and substrates for biosynthesis of steroid hormones (1).

Pakistan's annual consumption of edible oil is around 4.1 metric ton and is ranked amongst the top 5 global importer of edible oil. To fulfill the domestic demand, Pakistan imports 89% of edible oils, mainly from Australia, Canada, Ukraine, Malaysia and Indonesia (2).

Vanaspati-ghee (Banaspati), a product obtained by the partial hydrogenation of vegetable oil including, palm oil & palm olien, cotton seeds oil, rapeseed oil & mustard oil (3). Palm oil is the major (56-58%) and primary oil used as source for vanaspati-ghee production in Pakistan (4). In Pakistan vanaspati-ghee consumption is 20% higher than edible oil, mainly due to taste preference and product stability (5). Consumption of vanaspati-ghee is linked to elevated blood cholesterol levels, particularly when compared to edible oil (6,7,8).

Edible oil and vanaspati-ghee undergo quality deterioration as a result of oxidation, hydrolysis, polymerization and contamination, characterized by undesirable flavor, color, odor and nutritional value. Quality deterioration may result from improper processing, refining, packaging, storage and handling (9). Moreover rising international prices have increased the incentive to adulterate edible oils through the use of low-grade oils, recycled oils or poor-quality raw materials, thereby compromising the purity and overall quality of the product. The issue is very common in countries with weak regulatory frameworks and food safety enforcement mechanisms (10,11,12).

Excessive and Inferior-quality of edible oil and vanaspati ghee consumption is closely linked to a range of non-communicable diseases (NCDs) including, cardiovascular diseases, obesity, diabetes, dyslipidaemia, hypertension and certain cancers (10,11,13,14,15).

Quality of edible oil and vanaspati-ghee is assessed through a range of physicochemical parameters, including acid value, peroxide value, p-anisidine value, moisture content, iodine value, saponification value and vit A (9,17,18,19,20).

Pakistan Standard Quality Control Authority (PSQCA) serves as federal institution responsible for the formulation of national food safety and quality standards in Pakistan. The standards are developed under the framework and guidelines of the Codex Alimentarius, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and European food regulatory bodies, with local priorities and dietary practices to ensure contextual relevance. Provincial food authorities in Pakistan play a critical role in ensuring food safety and regulatory compliance, through regular market surveillance, food sampling and analysis to safeguard public health.

This study aims to highlight the overall quality index of edible-oil and vanaspati-ghee marketed in Balochistan in compliance to PSQCA formulated food safety and regulatory standards.

METHODOLGY

Commercially blended-oil (n=58) and vanaspati-ghee (n=35) samples from 17 different brands in each category (in their original packing) were collected by Balochistan Food Authority (BFA) during their routine monitoring drive, across various districts of Balochistan from January 2023 to January 2024. Samples collected were properly labelled and transported to BFA laboratory under standard condition for analysis.

The analysis included determination of quality parameters including, acid values, peroxide values and moisture content were analyzed, following AOAC Official Method 926.12, 940.28 and 965.33

respectively (21,22). p-anisidine value (secondary oxidation product) and vitamin A content were

assessed using iCheck Chroma 3 photometric analyzer (23). Refractive index was determined using digital Butyro-Refractometer at 40 °C (nD^{40}), following manufacturer’s protocol (24).

RESULTS

Physicochemical properties for vanaspati-ghee: Table 1 shows physicochemical properties of vanaspati-ghee samples (n=35) with noticeable variations across the brands compared to PSQCA and Codex Alimentarius specifications (Table. 2).

The acid values ranged between 0.03-0.54 mg KOH/g (mean 0.13 ± 0.113 mg KOH/g) with approximately 80% compliance. Peroxide value ranged between 0.45-13.17 meq O₂/kg (mean = 5.41 ± 3.52 meq O₂/kg) and 43% compliance. p-anisidine values between 0.5-7.8 (mean = 2.42 ± 1.66) and 77% compliance. Total oxidation values (Totox) ranged from 1.4 to 65 (mean = 16 ± 12.5) and approximately 75% compliance. The moisture content was between 0.11-3.3% (mean = $0.44 \pm 0.54\%$) with 3% compliance. The refractive index varied from 1.45 to 1.46 nD^{40} (mean = 1.4509 ± 0.003 nD^{40}) with approximately 91% compliance. iodine values ranged between 2.0-60 gI₂/100g (mean = 30.4 ± 12.35 gI₂/100g) with 6% compliance. Approximately 23% of vanaspati-ghee samples showed vit A within comparable limits.

samples (n=58), showing greater variability across the brands compare to PSQCA and Codex Alimentarius specifications (Table 2).

The acid values for the blended-oil ranged between 0.03-11.10 mg KOH/g (mean = 0.76 ± 1.94 mg KOH/g) with approximately 36% compliance. Peroxide value ranged between 0.10-13.8 meq O₂/kg (mean = 3.86 ± 3.35 meq O₂/kg) and approximately 90% compliance. p-anisidine values ranged from 1.0 to 11.0 (mean = 3.35 ± 2.57) and 56% compliance. Totox value ranged between 1.1-40.70 (mean = 11.6 ± 8.6) and 84.5% compliance. The moisture content ranged between 0.08-2.16% (mean = $0.33 \pm 0.28\%$) and 98% compliance.

Refractive index values varied from 1.45 to 1.46 nD^{40} (mean = 1.4509 ± 0.003 nD^{40}) and approximately 91% compliance. iodine values were between 2.0-60 gI₂/100g (mean = 30.4 ± 12.35), with 2% compliance. Approximately 14% of the blended-oil samples had vitamin A content in comparable limit to notational standards.

Table 1: Physicochemical properties of vanaspati-ghee

Parameter	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Acid Value (mg KOH/g)	35	0.03	0.54	0.13	0.113
Peroxide Value (meq O ₂ /kg)	35	0.45	13.17	5.41	3.52
p-Anisidine Value	35	0.50	7.80	2.42	1.66
Moisture Content (%)	34	0.11	3.30	0.44	0.54
Refractive Index	35	1.45	1.46	1.4509	0.003
Iodine Value (gI ₂ /100g)	35	2.00	60.00	30.40	12.35
Vitamin A (IU/kg)	35	3.00	129,936	26,364.5	30,309.16

Physicochemical properties for blended-oil: Table 3 highlights physicochemical properties of blended-oil

Table 2: PSQCA and Codex Alimentarius specified standards for vanaspati-ghee and blended-oil

Parameters	Acie value	Peroxide value	p-anisidine value	Totox	Moisture content	Refractive index	Iodine value	Vit A
Vanaspati-ghee	≤ 0.2 mg KOH/g	10 meq O ₂ /kg	≤ 3	≤ 20	≤ 0.2%	1.45-1.46 nD ⁴⁰	50-60 gI ₂ /100g	33,500-43,500 IU/kg
Blended-oil	≤ 0.2 mg KOH/g	10 meq O ₂ /kg	≤ 3	≤ 20	≤ 0.2%	1.45-1.46 nD ⁴⁰	≥ 80 gI ₂ /100g	33,500-43,500 IU/kg

Table 3: Physicochemical characteristics for blended-oil

Parameter	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Acid Value (mg KOH/g)	58	0.03	11.10	0.7591	1.94
Peroxide Value (meq O ₂ /kg)	58	0.10	18.2	4.15	3.8
p-Anisidine Value	58	1.0	11	3.35	2.57
Moisture Content (%)	58	0.08	2.16	0.33	0.28
Vitamin A (IU/kg)	58	0.0	234,300	22,735.16	40,338.78
Iodine Value (gI ₂ /100g)	58	2.00	80.00	43.5263	17.12
Refractive Index (nD ⁴⁰)	58	1.44	1.46	1.455	0.00381

DISCUSSION

High acid values for vanaspati-ghee (20%) and blended-oil (60%) samples are indicative of hydrolytic rancidity resulting from hydrolysis of triglycerides, possibly be due to poor quality control or prolonged storage. High peroxide value, above than permissible limits were observed for vanaspati-ghee (60%) and blended-oil (10%) samples, indicative of mild oxidation onset in vanaspati-ghee and more pronounced in oil samples, likely due to prolonged air exposure or improper packaging. High p-anisidine values in both the categories (vanaspati-ghee 23%, blended-oil 43%) samples, indicated moderate to high level of secondary oxidation products (aldehydes), indicative of advanced oxidative degradation of lipids. Total oxidation (Totox) value, which represents the combined effect of primary and secondary oxidation, were above the

permissible limit (≤20) in both the categories (vanaspati-ghee 25%, blended-oil 16.5%), indicative of oxidation onset, likely due to improper storage or extended shelf life.

Vanaspati-ghee (25%) and blended-oil (16.5%) samples in both the categories had Totox value above the permissible limit (≤20) indicative of overall oxidative deterioration, suggestive of oxidation onset, likely due to improper storage or extended shelf life. Majority of the samples in both the categories (vanaspati-ghee 97% and blended-oil 98%) had high moisture content than specified national standard limit, suggestive of inadequate dehydration, poor storage, making samples susceptible to hydrolytic rancidity, oxidative degradation and microbial growth. The refractive index for both the categories vanaspati-ghee (91%) and blended-oil (97%) respectively was in compliance to national standard specifications, consistent with the typical range for

hydrogenated fats, supported by the high saturation level indicated by low iodine values. Approximately 94% of the vanaspati ghee and 80% of blended-oil had iodine values above the national standard limit (vanaspati-ghee 50-60 gI₂/100g, blended-oil ≥80 gI₂/100g). This deviation from permissible limit may have resulted from excessive hydrogenation of vegetable oils, use of highly saturated base fats (palm oil, palm stearin or tallow) or use of recycled frying oil reduced through thermal oxidation. Both vanaspati-ghee and blended-oil samples displayed low vit A fortification profile (vanaspati-ghee 23%, blended-oil 14% respectively), reflecting non-compliance with Balochistan Food Fortification Act, 2021.

CONCLUSION

The findings highlight, an overall product deterioration and non-compliance to Pakistan standards (vanaspati-ghee 80% and blended-oil 100%) across 17 different brands in each category.

High variability in key quality parameters in both product categories were observed, characterized by high moisture, low iodine, low vit A profile, high primary (acid values) and secondary oxidation values (peroxide, p-anisidine), indicative of inconsistent synthetic protocols, poor processing and possible adulteration. The study highlighted lapses in regulatory compliance, underscoring the need for stricter regulatory monitoring and analysis. It is further recommended that BFA increases the frequency of monitoring, number of analysis and enlist all available brands across the province to ensure public health safety.

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